

Perceptions about Cosmetics among Feminine Working Consumers in Kanyakumari District

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Abstract

Today women are equal to men, they are involved in various activities like men. In the latest decade women are well educated and mostly they are employed. Self-confidence is important for women to face the problem in the society. Physical appearance is one of the important factors which enhance self-confidence in women. To improve their physical appearance women self-groom themselves using cosmetics. This study focuses on the perception of cosmetics among feminine consumers in Kanyakumari District. This study found that self-confidence, fresh feelings and attraction are the main motivating factors that influence the respondents in the study area to purchase cosmetics. High cost, poor quality and non-availability are the major problems faced by the respondents in the study area.

Keywords: Feminine, Cosmetics, Purchasing Behaviour.

Introduction

Indian Cosmetic Industry has had faster growth over the last couple of years. In that situation, the range of cosmetics and beauty products in our country has widened tremendously. Indian competitors have begun to manufacture products to cater to international needs. Organic and herbal cosmetics in India have greater demand in the international market. Some of the top cosmetics brands in India are Vive Cosmetics, VICC, Lotus Herbals, Colorbar, Cipla Limited, Lakme, Ag Industries, AM Enterprises, Biotique, Himalaya Herbals, L'Oreal India, Ayur herbs, Scot Derma etc. The top cosmetic products India exports are skin care products such as creams, serums, sunscreen lotions, and medicated ointment. Beauty and personal care products such as soaps, cleansers, oil and scrubs, Hair care products such as shampoos, gel, conditioner and oil. Oral care products such as mouthwash, toothpaste and mouth fresheners. Make products such as nail paints, lipsticks, lip gloss, hair colour and bleaches. There are lots of cosmetic products exported from India. Also, India plays a major role in the global beauty market as evidenced by the wide range of cosmetic products, it produces and exports.

Cosmetics are composed of mixtures of chemical compounds extracted from natural sources or synthetically created ones. Cosmetics help to conceal blemishes and to enhance natural features. Make-up can also add colour to a person's face, for enhancing the physical appearance women make use of cosmetics. A cosmetic is a substance used to clean, improve or change the complexion of the skin, hair and nails. Cosmetics include beauty preparations. It is used to repair damaged skin, hair, nails etc. In modern technology females are most urged to use cosmetics due to various factors such as dust and fumes, exposure to ultraviolet radiation from the sun etc, these factors cause harm to human beings. To enhance the

physical appearance they go behind the cosmetics. Beyond physical health, cosmetics can help to improve our mood, enhance our appearance and boost our self-esteem.

Statement of the problem

In modern times women are concentrating more on personal care as they are frequently moving out of their homes. In the olden days, cosmetics were considered a luxury for middle and lower classes but now it is a necessity. Expenditure on cosmetics occupies a prime share in the family's budgets. Working women consider cosmetics as a part of their lives as it brings self-confidence to them. At this juncture, several questions arise in the mind of the researchers, like what are the factors that motivate working feminine to purchase cosmetics? Are they satisfied while using cosmetics? Whether they are facing problems using cosmetics? To find fitting answers to these questions the study entitled, "Perception about cosmetics among the feminine consumers in Kanyakumari District." has been undertaken.

Scope of the study

This study covers working feminine consumers who use some of the make-up products which are face make-up products, eye make-up products, lip make-up products and nail make-up products. The face make-up product includes foundation, concealers, blushers and compact powder. Eye makeup products consist of eyebrow pencils, eye shadow, eyeliner and mascara. Lip makeup products include lipstick, lip gloss, and lip liner. Finally, nail make-up product includes nail polish and nail polish top coat.

Objectives of the study

The general objective of the study is to know the perception of cosmetics among feminine consumers in Kanyakumari District.

The following are the specific objectives

- To study the personal profile of the respondents.
- To find out the factors that motivate the respondents to purchase cosmetics.
- To know the source of knowledge about cosmetics and
- To find out the problems faced by the respondents.

Research Methodology

The study is based on primary and secondary data. The primary data were collected from 100 working women who consume cosmetics in Kanyakumari district. The samples were selected on a convenient basis. The secondary data were collected from articles, books, journals and websites. The collected data were analysed with the help of percentages, Garret's ranking and Likert's five-point scale.

Data & Discussions

The personal profiles of the respondents are studied by the researchers and presented in tabular form.

Table 1 - Personal profile of the respondents

S. No	Age	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	20-30	50	50
2	30-45	21	21
3	45-60	19	19
4	60 Above	10	10
S. No	Marital Status	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Married	44	44
2	Single	56	56

S. No.	Family structure	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Joint	34	34
2	Nuclear	66	66
S. No.	Working Status	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Private	80	80
2	Government	20	20

Source: Primary data

The respondents were asked to indicate their responses by questionnaire. From the above table, it can be seen that out of 100 respondents, 50% of the respondents belong to the age group between 20-30 years and only 10% of the respondents are in the age group of above 60 years. It is inferred from the above analysis that the majority of the respondents in the age group between 20-30 years wish to use cosmetics more. 56% of the respondents are single and the remaining 44% of the respondents are married. This shows most of the unmarried feminine consumers wish to use cosmetics more. 34% of the respondents belong to a joint family and 66% of the respondents belong to a nuclear family. It shows that the majority of respondents belonging to the nuclear family consume cosmetics. 80% of the respondents are working in the private sector and 20% of the respondents are working in the Government sector. It shows that self-confidence is important to the private employee so, they are using cosmetics to enhance their appearance.

Table 2 - Sources of Knowledge

S.No	Sources	No. of respondent	Percentage
1	Social media	42	42
2	Television	20	20
3	Neighbour and Relatives	12	12
4	Friends and Colleagues	26	26

Source: Primary data

The above table reveals that 42% of the respondents know the product through social media, 26% of the respondents know through Friends and Colleagues, 20% of the respondents know through Television and 12% of the respondents know through Friends and Relatives. It indicates social media leads today's generation.

Table 3 - Motivational factors

S.No.	Factors	Average Score	Rank
1	Improves Self Confidence	67.43	I
2	Feel Fresh	52.02	II
3	Attract Others	50.07	III
4	Get young look	48.55	IV
5	Affordable Cost	46.37	V

Source: Primary data

A scrutiny of the above table reveals that the three major factors that influence the respondents to purchase cosmetics Self Confidence (I Rank), Feeling fresh (II Rank) and attracting others (III Rank).

Table 4 - Satisfaction Level of the Respondents

Factors	H.S	S	N	D.S	H.D.S	Total respondent	Total score	Mean score	Rank
Reasonable price	38(190)	36(144)	10(30)	8(16)	8(8)	100	388	3.88	I
Good quality	30(150)	34(136)	20(60)	10(20)	6(6)	100	372	3.72	II
Correct quality	10(50)	30(120)	30(90)	16(32)	14(14)	100	306	3.06	IV
Availability	14(70)	30(120)	20(60)	24(48)	12(12)	100	310	3.10	III
Last for a long time	10(50)	26(104)	30(90)	20(40)	14(14)	100	298	2.98	VII
Offers	10(60)	22(88)	28(84)	20(40)	20(20)	100	292	2.92	VIII
Package	20(100)	20(80)	20(60)	20(40)	20(20)	100	300	3	VI
Chemical free	20(100)	20(80)	20(60)	25(50)	15(15)	100	305	3.05	V

Source: Primary data

Table 4 reveals that the respondents are highly satisfied regarding the 'reasonable price' of the product it got the first rank, the good quality got the second rank and availability got the third rank. The last rank is for offers. This shows the respondents are highly satisfied with the reasonable price of the product and they are not satisfied with the offers provided by the sellers.

Table 5 - Problems

S.No.	Problems	Average	Rank
1	Costly	57.26	I
2	Non-availability	49.2	III
3	Poor quality	52.34	II
4	Cheating	46.3	VI
5	Less quality	47.08	V
6	Causing allergy	47.38	IV

Source: Primary data

From Table 5 which is based on Garret's ranking technique, it was revealed that 'costly' is the major problem with the highest average score of 57.26. Accordingly 'poor quality' with an average score of 52.34 is ranked second. The average score of 49.2 is for 'non-availability' and it is ranked third, fourth and fifth rank is for 'causing allergy' for which the average score is 47.38 and 'less quality' for which the average score is 47.08 and the last rank is for 'cheating' for which the average score is 46.3. High cost, low quality and non-availability are the major problems faced by the respondents in the study area.

Suggestion

- The respondents are not satisfied with the offers given by the sellers of cosmetics. So, the sellers can give different types of offers for their products to attract consumers.

- Quality is very important for cosmetics as it provides many side effects to the users. The manufacturers must produce the cosmetics with the utmost care as it affects the health of the consumers.
- Appropriate pricing strategies should be formulated for different types of cosmetic products.
- Retailers should make efforts to retain their regular and future customers by serving upgraded products to them.
- To enhance the level of satisfaction of feminine consumers, it is recommended to enhance the quality, suitability and fragrance of cosmetics by the manufacturers through proper research and development efforts.

Conclusion

Every woman's everlasting desire is to stay young and beautiful always. Make-up products are a powerful weapon in the hands of the feminine which transforms normal-looking people into beautiful. This study found that self-confidence, fresh feelings and attraction are the main motivating factors that influence the respondents in the study area to purchase cosmetics. High cost, poor quality and non -availability are the major problems faced by the respondents in the study area. Designing effective tools and regulations to monitor the cosmetic market and improve the knowledge of cosmetics are important to ensure safe cosmetic usage by feminine consumers.

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